

InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

Grant agreement No 101091099

D1.1. ETHICS PRINCIPLES AND GUIDELINES FOR PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA

Ethics principles and guidelines for protection of personal data

Summary

This document outlines the ethical principles and guidelines for protecting personal data in the InBestSoil project. Its purpose is to establish a framework for all project partners to follow in order to safeguard the privacy and security of stakeholders involved in the project. It is essential that all project partners adhere to these ethical principles, as failure to do so may result in legal and reputational consequences.

A control will be established in all the actions of the project to ensure that a thorough and effective control of the data provided by the stakeholders involved is carried out. The control of personal information will be done, starting with the identification of the work packages and activities where this information is needed. This also includes the type of information to be requested from participants and the means to be used (surveys, questionnaires, interviews, workshops, etc.), as well as the list of partners with whom this information will be shared. Information regarding data storage, protection, and destruction is detailed in this document. A template is included at the end, which will be provided to stakeholders participating in the project, detailing general information about the project, as well as a series of consents provided to obtain and use the information.

Deliverable Number		Work Package	
D1.1		WP1	
Lead Beneficiary		Deliverable Author(s)	
UVigo		Diego Soto Gómez [UVigo] Raúl Zornoza Belmonte [UPCT]	
Versions (updates)		Date	
V1		14.03.2023	
V2		27.03.2023	
Deliverable Quality Check		Date	
Diego Soto Gómez [UVigo]		31.03.2023	
Planned Delivery Date		Final Delivery Date	
M1 (31.03.2023)		M3	
Type of deliverable	R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethycs	x
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	x
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

Table of content

- 1. Introduction: required information and ethical principles4
- 2. Tasks and work packages that require personal information6
- 3. Principles for personal data obtention and processing.....8
 - 3.1. Obtention of data from stakeholders8
 - 3.2. Procedures for storage, protection, detection, and destruction8
- 4. Annex 1. InBestSoil project information and consent form 10

1. Introduction: required information and ethical principles

The InBestSoil (IBS) is a multi-stakeholder project in which co-creation, co-design and co-innovation activities will involve stakeholders (STHs) from multiple fields. These activities include the development of new business models based on soil health, the creation of appropriate incentives for each land use and geographic area, and the development of policies based on the needs of each specific case. For the development of all these tasks, it is essential to obtain data from different STHs by conducting interviews and questionnaires, for example, in which it will be necessary to include certain personal information. For example, in order to take into account, the gender perspective and its influence on our models (i.e., to be able to include gender as a factor), we need to know with which gender the interviewed STHs identify themselves. Therefore, it will be necessary to include this type of inquiry in the set of questions we will ask potential STHs.

Regarding general ethical principles, the partners have agreed in the Grant Agreement that they will respect "the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles". Furthermore, the project partners commit themselves to respect the basic values of the EU "such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities". The project partners will always take into account "the principle of proportionality, the right to privacy, the right to the protection of personal data, the right to the physical and mental integrity of persons, the right to non-discrimination, the need to ensure protection of the environment and high levels of human health protection".

Of course, the fundamental principle of research integrity will be respected, following the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA (All European Academies) European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity). This implies:

- "reliability in ensuring the quality of research reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources
- honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair and unbiased way
- respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment
- accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts"

On the other hand, regarding the protection of the privacy of the STHs involved and their personal data, the partners have agreed in the Grant Agreement that such data will be processed "under the responsibility of the data controller of the granting authority in accordance with and for the purposes set out in the Portal Privacy Statement". In this case, considering that the granting authority is the

European Commission, the data processing is subject to Regulation 2018/1725 15 ("Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2018 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and Decision No 1247/2002/EC (OJ L 295, 21.11.2018, p. 39)"). It has also been agreed in the Grant Agreement that the project partners will process data in accordance with Regulation 2016/679 16 ("Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC ('GDPR') (OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1)"). Therefore, all project partners have committed that personal data will be processed lawfully, fairly and transparently in relation to the data subjects; collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and processed in accordance with these three principles; adequate and relevant for the purpose for which it is required; up-to-date; accurate; retained in a form that allows identification of data subjects during the period in which the data will be used; and that an appropriate security system is in place for accessing the data. Access by members to this data shall be on a strictly necessary basis, and the confidentiality of such data shall be guaranteed.

In order to make some concepts clear, we copy below some definitions from article four of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April 2016:

- Personal data "means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person".
- Processing "means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction".
- Consent of the data subject "means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her".

2. Tasks and work packages that require personal information

In some IBS work packages (WPs) it will not be necessary to obtain or process sensitive information. In this section, we will identify those WPs where private information will be required, as well as the tasks that include obtaining or using that information.

Within WP2:

- *Task 2.1. Analysis and mapping of stakeholders for each LH and LL.* In this task, it will be necessary to obtain information from key STHs within the different lighthouses and living labs.
- *Task 2.4. From local to regional/national: building LLs based on existing LHs.* For the creation of new LLs, it will be necessary to collect more information on potential STHs that would be willing to be part of these LLs.

Within WP3:

- *Task 3.1. Co-definition of suitable indicators and standardized metrics for the LCA and evaluation of ecosystem services and disservices provided by soil in different land uses.* The indicators to be measured will be defined jointly, with the active participation of the STHs, and obtaining information from them.

Within WP4:

- *Task 4.1. Sustainable business models: state of the art of current archetypes, drivers and barriers.* For the analysis of the state of the art of business models based on the improvement of soil quality, the information obtained through the literature search will be complemented with interviews with STHs.
- *Task 4.2. Ex-post evaluation of carbon farming business models.* For the ex-post evaluation of the selected business models, information obtained from interviews with STHs will be used.
- *Task 4.3. Ex-post evaluation of forestry business models.* As in the previous task, part of this task consists of questionnaires to STHs.

Within WP5

- *Task 5.2. Explore the potential of socio-ecological and technological innovation pathways to support the development of business strategies/cases for soil health.* This task will require the participation and gathering of information from the existing communities around our LLs/LHs, with the participation of different types of STHs.
- *Task 5.3. Design of new business models for soil health: the Triple Layer Business Model Canvas.* For the design of new business models, it will be essential to have the participation of STHs from all the value chain, and we will try to collect information from all of them.

Within WP6

- *Task 6.1. Stocktaking: mapping review of policy and economic incentives for soil health.* For this task, it will be necessary to perform structured interviews with 15-20 knowledgeable experts and representatives of organizations.

Within WP7:

- *Task 7.2. Dissemination strategy.* The dissemination strategy includes tasks such as the organization of workshops, seminars, field demonstrations and talks in universities in which STHs will participate and information will be collected from them.

In WP1, Task 1.2 Data Management, private information will not be processed directly, but the mechanisms to store and share part of this information will be defined. This task includes the development of the Data Management Plan, in which we will define the types of data that will be generated throughout the project, as well as the description of the data and the procedures for sharing, archiving and preserving this data.

Considering the above, it will be necessary to share personal information with partners from the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Latvia, Lithuania, the United Kingdom and Switzerland.

3. Principles for personal data obtention and processing

3.1. Obtention of data from stakeholders

The IBS project requires obtaining data from different stakeholder profiles for the activities mentioned in the previous section. In task 2.1 Analysis and mapping of stakeholders for each LH and LL, a mapping of all STHs related to the different LLs/LHs of the project will be carried out. This task will be coordinated by Zabala Innovation, and will be updated with new STHs throughout the duration of the project. For this task, we will have the collaboration of the different case study coordinators, as well as the members of the consortium in general.

Data will be collected through surveys, questionnaires, interviews, etc., and by different means, using the stakeholder collaborative platform, mails or phone calls, or during workshops, seminars, webinars, field demonstrations, fairs, congresses, etc.

Prior to data collection, an explanation of the project, the data necessary to achieve the objectives and the rights of the STH regarding these data will be provided. This information will be provided along with a consent template that the concerned STH must sign if he/she agrees with the conditions expressed in it. An example of a consent template is provided in Annex 1. If required by the survey, further information will be provided to the STHs. Both the participation of the STHs and the collection of data will be done without exerting pressure, and by providing accurate and reliable information.

3.2. Procedures for storage, protection, detection, and destruction

Data processing will be done following Article 5 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of April 27, 2016. We can summarize this article in the following points:

- The principles of lawfulness, fairness, and transparency regarding private data will be followed.
- Data will be collected and processed for specific and legitimate purposes.
- Only indispensable data will be collected, the most appropriate for the task to be carried out. The data must be up-to-date and accurate.
- Information will be kept in such a way that the identification of the data subjects is possible for the duration of the processing.
- The data will be protected: its security will be maintained at all times, so that it is not used unlawfully, lost or damaged.

In order to store and protect the data, the project team will use an internal password-protected Microsoft Teams 365 hosted by UPCT, which only specific members of the consortium will have access (General Folder). The information shared with all partners will be anonymized, i.e., private information will be

removed. This will be preserved, but kept in a second folder in Teams (Coordination Folder) to which only WPs coordinators will have access.

All personal data will be destroyed upon request or at the end of the project (up to 36 months after the end of InBestSoil). Scientific information will be kept anonymous at the end of the project, and this information will not be made public until 3 years after the end of the project. Issues concerning this type of data are summarized in the Data management plan (DPM).

4. Annex 1. InBestSoil project information and consent form

Informative Sheet/Informed Consent Template

Project title: Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil (Horizon Europe Project 101091099)

Project coordinator: Diego Soto Gómez, University of Vigo.

Work Package/ Lighthouse/ Living Lab Coordinator: **[Name, institutional affiliation].**

About the project: InBestSoil main research question is: Can we maintain and restore soil health and resilience to climate change impacts by developing innovative business models and incentive tools based on the economic valuation of ecosystem services provided by soil? To this end, InBestSoil hypothesizes that translating the ecosystem services provided by healthy soils and the impacts of soil interventions into monetary values, and co-designing business models and incentives related to these values, will increase awareness of opportunities to invest in soil health, and thus establish new businesses to maintain and restore soil health in Europe. We will attempt to validate this hypothesis using lighthouses (LHs) and living laboratories (LLs) as hubs. We consider a LH as a place for the demonstration of long-term solutions, which are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement, and a LL as the collaboration between some research and innovation ecosystems, involving regional stakeholders in systemic research and co-design, to jointly improve the effectiveness of new practices on soil health.

Purpose of your participation: You are invited to be part of our research study on **INDICATE/EXPLORE THE TASK/ACTIVITY YOU ARE ASKED TO PARTICIPATE IN** as part of the InBestSoil project. You are asked to participate in **CHOOSE ACTIVITY/ ACTIVITIES FROM THE LIST***.

Time of participation: The project lasts four years (from 2023 to 2026).

Risks and Benefits: The risks associated to this study are **SELECT RISK/ RISKS FROM THE LIST CONSIDERING THE TASK TO BE PERFORMED****. Because of the innovative nature of the techniques being tried in the project, the results may not be as expected, including **LOSS OF BENEFITS*****, and there is no guarantee or assurance that you will receive any benefit from this study. Your choice whether to participate in this study will not affect your participation in other InBestSoil events and activities.

Reimbursement: You will not receive any reimbursement as payment for your participation.

Rights: Your participation is voluntary, and you have the right to decline to participate and to remove your participation, samples, or data at any time with no

consequences. You have the right to decline to answer certain questions. Your name and personal contact information will always be kept confidential, will never be made public, trackable or accessible, and you will never be identified or linked to the samples or data. You will always be the owner of the data and samples collected. You will be able to access the data by personal communication and/or report.

Use of data/samples: The collected materials and data will be part of studies that may be presented at scientific or professional meetings or published in scientific or professional journals for communication and dissemination purposes of the InBestSoil project. Personal Data will be used only for administrative, operational, accounting, research and monitoring purposes that are necessary for the safe and reliable execution of InBestSoil, without affecting the individual's rights under the relevant laws.

Data Storage, Security, Retention, and Destruction: Data will be safely stored in a private InBestSoil Teams folder. The University of Cartagena protects this folder from viruses and data hacking, and performs regular backups. In the unlikely event of chance findings, you will be notified to decide whether you wish to delete your data. Personal Data will be retained until data derived from samples, surveys, questionnaires, or interviews are scientifically processed and published, and will be destroyed after a period of 18 months following publication. By default, Personal Data will be destroyed 36 months after the end of the InBestSoil.

Contact information: If you have any questions, concerns or complaints about this research, its procedures, risks and benefits, please contact the Project Coordinator (Dr. Diego Soto Gómez; disoto@uvigo.es; +34 660679251). [Insert here Work Package/ Lighthouse/ Living Lab Coordinator contact information.](#)

Independent contact: If you are dissatisfied with the way this study is being conducted, or if you have any general concerns, complaints, or questions about the research or your rights as a participant, please contact Sabela González (R&D technician, not involved in the project), Universidade de Vigo (dir.inv.opi@uvigo.gal, +34 986 818639) to speak with someone independent of the research team.

*Events organized by the InBestSoil consortium, surveys, questionnaires and interviews, lighthouses, living labs, or in video/audio recordings about your experience as an end user or stakeholder or giving permission to collect samples.

** Risks may be economic/financial or associated with impacts on profits, plant health and safety, data protection, data management, privacy or reputation.

*** Only applicable to living labs. Include that any legal liability will affect the InBestSoil project in case of lost profits.

Indicate Yes or No:

- I give consent to be audiotaped during this study: ___Yes ___No
- I give consent to be videotaped during this study: ___Yes ___No
- I give consent for registration of data resulting from this study to be used at scientific or professional meetings or published in scientific or professional journals for communication and dissemination purposes: ___Yes ___No
- I give consent for audio and/or videos resulting from this study to be used at scientific or professional meetings or published in scientific or professional journals for communication and dissemination purposes: ___Yes ___No
- On default, your identity (name and contact data) will be retained anonymous and confidential, unless you give explicit consent to reveal your identity: __Yes

Signed, on duplicate, so that one copy of this signed and dated consent form is for you to keep.

NAME:

ORGANIZATION:

DATE:

SIGNATURE
